

Smart real-time vehicle tracking system with safe travel

Sherrin Banu J^{1,*}, Kokilavani M², Keerthana V³, Murugesan M⁴

¹Assistant Professor, Department of EEE, M.I.E.T. Engineering College, Trichy, India

^{2,3}Assistant Professor, Department of ECE, M.I.E.T. Engineering College, Trichy, India

⁴Librarian, M.I.E.T. Engineering College, Trichy, India

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ABSTRACT

In our day to day life travelling plays a major role, but we find difficult to find out public transport location and time of arrival. In this project we are using system tracker device (GPS/GPRS, sensor units,) which attached with the public transport. The bus name which is attached with the bus. The bus name plate details are built in fixed with the device. The system unit consist of temperature sensor and beam detector to prevent fire accident, Anti-lock Brake System (ABS) sensor to monitor the brake control, tier puncture monitoring system to detect. The system tracker indicates the passengers about the bus arrival timing and next stopping details in all the terminals in the route using IOT technology. In case of the bus breakdown in between the route then the sensor detects the fault is sent to the main bus terminus for alternative arrangement. This information also is announced and displayed in LCD board and message/ app notification is sent to the passenger regarding alternative bus is arranged for. For the travelers inside the bus next boarding point details are intimated as announcement as well as in message. We can app or messaging system in case of app failure to indicate about the boarding point details ticket fare details, and arrivals timing of bus to that particular stopping. People who are not having android phone can use helpline number and can get automatic details.

Keywords

IoT, sensor unit, app, messaging, GPRS unit

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*Address Correspondence to E-mail: sherrinbanu2@gmail.com

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1. Introduction

Public transport is a fast and convenient way of travel, but there are many issues related to it. Challenges in current public transport system are: how to estimate the exact arrival time of vehicle and real tracking of vehicle. Solution of these two problems directly save the user time and provide better management for scheduling of vehicles. Many proposals exist in the literature to address above mentioned issues. Keeping the need of intelligent transportation system, this paper provides comparative analysis of all the state-of-art existing proposals. Tracking the vehicles generally takes two types of data: historical and real time data. For real time tracking of vehicles, Global Positioning System (GPS), sensors, Internet of Things (IoT) devices, etc., are used. Due to generation of huge amount of data from IoT enabled devices present in transport system, kalman filtering, artificial neural network, data analytics and machine learning are also used for better scheduling of vehicles. In last section we provide the open issues and challenges that needs to be taken care while designing the Intelligent Transport System (ITS).

This project is mainly very useful for women who are travelling in public transport also school going children who are using public transport and elderly people It Is Very Useful for the People Who Are Travelling during Night Time, For Women Who Are Waiting for public transport in the boarding point. To prevent accident due to miscellaneous failure.

Public transport is an essential and mandatory one for every person to travel to work or to their home after work. If in case there are many issues in knowing about the details of public transport people couldn't find the alternative quite easily. This system helps in knowing all the details about the public transport so that people find it easy. Abdullah Al Hafiz Khan dealt with the design and development of Bus Management & Road Accident Prevention System for Smart Cities. This paper explains Whenever the driver will be either drowsy or will be in the wrong lane, the pi camera kept in front of him will trace the abnormality, and also the LED will be on. As a result, the driver will be alerted for safe driving. As we all know, prevention is better than cure, so our motto is to decrease the number of road accidents to a noticeable extent by preventing the vital cause of reckless driving. Fatin Balkis Binti Alzahri in his paper discussed the process of developing a Vehicle Tracking Device (VTD). VTD is a tracking device focusing on vehicles that use Short Message Service (SMS). VTD will give information of location coordinate to mobile phone whenever there is a request for it through the SMS.

The only major constraint is that implementation cost is high and maintenance of the entire system requires more attention. Other than these this helps the public people to easily get the details regarding the public transport and tracking is also very simple. It can be widely used in school buses and also in

other transports.

The public transport so far available do not have any such system to rectify the faults or failure and also details of the vehicles are not sent to the people who are waiting for the transport. Time Wastage in waiting for public transport. Ladies find difficult to wait for transport during night time. Some people find difficult to find cash to pay while travelling because they are not aware of the ticket fare and sometimes due to over crowdedness ticket collector not able to get the ticket fare from the passengers.

2. Experimental setup

In this project we are using system tracker device (GPS/GPRS, sensor units) which attached with the public transport. The bus name which is attached with the bus. The bus name plate details are built in fixed with the device. The system unit consists of temperature sensor and beam detector to prevent fire accident, anti-lock brake system (ABS) sensor to monitor the brake control, tier puncture monitoring system to detect (TPMS) as shown in the figure 1.

The object sensor is used to detect the objects in rear and far position with PLC as a controller and accident can be controlled by changing the position of the wheel as shown in the figure2. The system tracker indicates the passengers about the bus arrival timing and next stopping details in all the terminals in the route using IOT technology (ESP32 wifi Bluetooth controller) as shown in the figure 3.

In case of the bus breakdown in between the route then the sensor detects and intimates the tracking system, the fault is sent to the main bus terminus Trough the PLC controller for alternative arrangement.

The overall block diagram of the experimental setup

Figure 1. Overall Communication System.

Figure 2. General block diagram of communication

Figure 3. Interfacing of Arduino and IOT module

Speed of the public transport can be controlled automatically using the speed controller device operated with PLC controller. This information also is announced and displayed in LCD board and message/ app notification is sent to the passenger regarding alternative bus is arranged for. For the travelers inside the bus next boarding point details are intimated as announcement as well as in message as shown in the figure 2.

We can app or messaging system in case of app failure to indicate about the boarding point details ticket fare details, and arrivals timing of bus to that particular stopping. People who are not having android phone can use helpline number and can get automatic details.

3. Conclusion

Thus, the public transport so far available do not have any such system to rectify the faults or failure and also details of the vehicles are not sent to the people who are waiting for the transport. Time Wastage in waiting for public transport. Ladies find difficult to wait for transport during night time. Some people find difficult to find cash to pay while travelling because they are not aware of the ticket fare and sometimes due to over

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